

ENSURING SAFE HANDLING AND DISPOSAL OF INJECTION EQUIPMENTS IN HEALTH FACILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper assessed the handling and safe disposal of injection equipment in the health facilities. It identified the predominant ways of handling injection materials and methods employed for safe disposal of waste hospitals. The study revealed that though open burning seemed a reliable method of safe disposal due its benefit of mass reduction in the quantity of waste, destruction of disease causing organisms and low cost of management, the massive uncontrolled smoke emanating during open burning, generates air pollution which poses a great threat to public health. There are also the risks of damage to crops of the nearby farmlands due to chemical constituents of the hospital's waste placed at the dumpsite prior to open burning. Furthermore, findings showed that the dumpsites posed health risks and altered the aesthetics of the surroundings. There was a strong correlation between the level of precipitation on safe waste management between patients and staff and effectiveness of safe disposal. The study recommends among others careful sorting of waste before disposal, and restriction of farming activities around the dumpsites.

INTRODUCTION

Injections are the most common health-care procedure worldwide. In developing and transitional countries alone, some 16 billion injections are administered each year, (Coker et al, 2019). About 90% of injections are given for therapeutic purposes while 5 to 10% are given for preventive services, such as immunization and family planning. The majority of therapeutic injections in developing and transitional countries are unnecessary. A safe injection does not harm the recipient, does not expose the health-care worker to any avoidable risk and does not result in waste that is dangerous for the community, (FEPA, 1991).

Environmental Challenges of 20th and 21st century indicates that waste

in whatever form or classification—solid, liquid or gaseous have become a major consequence of modernization and economic development as reported by Tsiboe and Marbell, (2014). There is a significant concern expressed by environmentalists about wastes generated in hospitals and other healthcare facilities which are not properly managed. Health care activities involve protecting the environment, curing lives.

However, illnesses/diseases and saving in the course of these activities, wastes are generated, 20 percent of which expose humans to risk of infections, trauma, chemical or radiation exposure and sometimes death. Hospital wastes are considered

Hazardous and Nonhazardous. Hazardous wastes are those that are majorly generated in the laboratory and contain toxic substances. Industrial and hospital wastes are considered hazardous as they may contain toxic substances. Certain types of household wastes are also hazardous. Hazardous wastes could be highly toxic to humans, animals and plants and are corrosive, highly inflammable, or explosive; and can thus react when exposed to certain things like gases (Babatola, 2018). It has been reported that 75-90% of the waste produced by health care institutions are non-risk as they are generated from administrative and housekeeping/maintenance of health care establishment, the remaining 10-25% waste is regarded as 'hazardous' and may create a variety of health risks. Manyele, (2014) describes medical wastes as any solid waste generated in the diagnosis, treatment or immunization of human beings or animals as well as in related researches, production or testing of biological from all types of healthcare institutions, including hospitals, clinics, doctor offices and medical laboratories. As reported by Omojasola et al (2019), the waste produced in the course of health care activities carries a higher potential for infection and injury than any other types of waste. It is essential to have reliable method for its safe handling and disposal. Poor management of waste have exposed medical staff, waste –handling workers

and the surrounding communities to infections, toxic effects and injuries, a situation that poses a serious health problem in most developing parts of the world (WHO, 2019).

This review was designed to examine the safe handling and disposal of injection equipment in health facilities with the following objectives:

1. To outline safe methods of handling injection equipments
2. To identify the types of wastes generated in the Health Facilities
3. To examine the methods of safe disposal of injection equipments in healthcare facilities
4. To find out how the methods used in disposing injection equipments affects health and environment.

Concept of Waste

Waste can be in a solid, liquid or in a gaseous form. A product, material or container is not considered waste until someone throws it away. Waste is more easily recognized than defined. Something can become waste when it is no longer useful to the owner or it has been used for purpose it was meant to serve as opined by Freduah, (2014).

Impact of Health Care Waste on Human Health

According to the WHO (2019), the global life expectancy is increasing year after year. However, deaths due to infectious diseases are increasing. A study conducted by the WHO in 2016,

reveals that more than 50,000 people die every day from infectious diseases. One of major causes for the increase in infectious diseases is improper waste management. A lot of infections and diseases are documented to spread through bio-medical waste. Tuberculosis, pneumonia, diarrhoeal diseases, tetanus, whooping cough etc., are some common diseases that spread due to improper waste management (Chitins et al, 2012; Chitins et al, 2013; Tudor et al, 2015; Marinkovic et al, 2015). Occupational health concerns exist for janitorial and laundry workers, nurses, emergency medical personnel, and refuse workers. Injuries from sharps and exposure to harmful chemical waste and radioactive waste also cause health hazards to employees in institutions generating bio-medical waste. Proper management of waste can solve the problem of occupational hazards to a large extent (Patil and Shekar, 2011).

Impact of Health care Waste on the Environment

Hospital waste is potentially dangerous, since it may possess pathogenic agents. Some of the pathogenic organisms are dangerous, because they may be resistant to treatment and possess high pathogenicity. Inadequate waste management will cause environmental pollution, unpleasant smell, growth and multiplication of

insects, rodents and worms and may lead to the transmission of diseases like typhoid, cholera, hepatitis and AIDS through injuries from syringes and needles contaminated with human blood (Henry and Heinke, 2016). The inefficient handling of health care waste is more likely to cause problems such as blood borne pathogens to the groups at highest risk, namely; healthcare staff, scavengers, and municipal workers (from needle sticks for example, if the safe wastes are with domestic wastes). There is particular concern about infection with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and hepatitis viruses B and C, for which there is strong evidence of transmission via healthcare waste (WHO 2019). The general public's health is adversely affected by health care waste. Improper practices such as dumping of health care waste in municipal dustbins, open spaces, water bodies' etc. could lead to the spread of diseases. (Manohaet al, 2018; Da silvanet al, 2015) reported that emissions from incinerators and open burning could also result in exposure to harmful gases which can cause cancer and respiratory diseases. Plastic waste can choke animals, which scavenge on openly dumped waste. Injuries from sharps health care objects are common feature-affecting animals. Harmful chemicals such as dioxins and furans can cause serious health hazards to animals and

birds. Certain heavy metals could affect the reproductive health of the animals as (Code & Christic, 2019) indicated.

Safe Waste Disposal Strategies

Handling, sorting, disinfection, storage, transportation and final disposal are vital steps for safe and scientific management of waste in any health care establishment (Acharya and Meeta2010). Health care waste can be managed properly by ensuring proper

sorting at the source, the use of accurate packaging (leak resistant, puncture resistant and not susceptible to degradation by cleaning agents in case the packaging is reused), appropriate colour coding, proper in-house movement of waste (minimizing employee exposure to waste in a workplace), designating waste storage areas and ensuring safe disposal.

INJECTION EQUIPMENT IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

Injection equipments form the buck of waste in the health system. It is used in every unit or department in the process of care, prevention and treatment of disease. To ensure safe disposal of injection equipments in health care facilities, it is important to understand the various types to know how to properly handle them and ensure their safe disposal.

Types of injection equipment

The following equipment are used to administer injectables:

Equipment	Remarks
1. Auto-disable (AD) syringes	Equipment of choice
2. Prefilled AD injection devices	Available for some antigens only
3. Reusable syringes and needles	Not recommended
4. Single use disposable (non AD) syringes and needles	For mixing purposes only

Figure 2: Injection equipment

Auto-disable (AD) syringes

AD syringes are self-locking syringes that can be used only once. AD syringes are the preferred equipment for all types of immunization sessions. Every AD syringe is sterilized and sealed by the manufacturer. There are several types of AD syringes. Most AD syringes have fixed needles. Others have detachable needles that fit only the specific AD syringe they accompany.

These needles cannot be used with a standard syringe. Some AD syringes are individually packaged in plastic or paper packets, others are boxed in bulk. All AD syringes have plastic caps to keep the needle sterile, and some also have caps on the plungers. There are different AD syringes to give BCG vaccine and to give the other vaccines. Each type of AD syringe requires health workers to use a specific technique to administer

injectables. Below are general steps to follow when using AD syringes. These steps must be refined depending on the specific AD syringe you are using.

General steps for using AD syringes:

- ❖ Remove the syringe and needle from plastic wrapping (peel open the syringe plunger end of the package) or detach the plastic caps.
- ❖ Fix the needle to the syringe if it is not already in place. Take off the needle cap without touching the needle. *NOTE:* The plunger can go back and forth only once, so health workers should not move the plunger unnecessarily and should not try to inject air into the vial, as this will disable the syringe.
- ❖ Insert the needle in the vaccine vial and bring the tip of the needle to the lowest part of the bottom of the vial.
- ❖ Pull the plunger back to fill the syringe. The plunger will automatically stop just past the 0.05 ml/0.50 ml mark and you will hear a “click.”
- ❖ Keep the needle tip in the fluid at all times, making sure to empty the full contents of the vial. Remove the needle from the vial. To remove air bubbles, hold the syringe upright and tap the barrel. Then carefully push to the close mark.
- ❖ Locate the injection site.
- ❖ Push the plunger forward and

inject the vaccine. After injection, the plunger will automatically lock and the syringe cannot be reused. Do not re-cap the needle after use.

- ❖ Dispose of the needle and syringe in a safety box: a leak-proof, puncture resistant container for safe waste management.

Advantages of AD syringes:

- They can only be used once.
- They eliminate the patient-to-patient disease transmission caused by the use of contaminated needles and syringes.
- They save time for health workers from the heavy work of sterilization.

Prefilled AD injection devices

Prefilled AD injection devices are single-dose packets with a needle affixed by the manufacturer. This type of injection device can be used only once.

Hepatitis B vaccine and tetanus toxoid are currently available in prefilled AD injection devices. Hepatitis B prefilled AD injection devices are used primarily to provide hepatitis B vaccine to newborns in their homes. Tetanus toxoid prefilled AD injection devices are used to provide TT vaccine to women of childbearing age in their homes and during mass campaigns. Every prefilled AD injection device is sterilized and sealed in its own foil

package by the manufacturer. The vaccine is contained in a sealed, bubble-like reservoir that prevents it from coming in contact with the needle until the administration. To prepare or “activate” the prefilled AD injection device, push the needle shield (or cap) into the port. This opens the fluid path between the needle and the reservoir that contains the vaccine. Then, remove the needle shield, insert the needle into the injection site, and deliver the dose by squeezing the reservoir until it is empty. After use, the prefilled AD devices should be collected in a safety box for final disposal.

Advantages of prefilled AD injection devices:

Prefilled AD injection devices have the same advantages as AD syringes. In addition:

- They prevent vaccine contamination.
- They ensure an accurate dose.
- They deliver vaccine and syringe together in the same set.
- Syringe and vaccine can be ordered with a single request.
- They contain less plastic than a syringe, so waste is reduced.
- The unit-dose device reduces the vaccine waste that occurs when using multidose vials.

Sterilizable syringes and needles

Sterilizable syringes and needles are

no longer recommended for use in the EPI however they are still used in some countries, but should be phased out gradually with AD syringes are becoming preference. For countries where they are still being used, their sterility must be guaranteed by complying with the following:

- The health workers can be sure to comply with cleaning and sterilization procedures between each use.
- The health workers will routinely use time, steam and temperature indicators (TSTs) for each sterilization.
- Supervisors can verify these procedures.
- Immediately after use, the syringes and needles must be flushed with clean water and soaked in clean water. They must be carefully cleaned at the end of the session.
- Before use, they must be steam-sterilized for 20 minutes at a temperature between 121°C and 126°C.
- You must dispose of sterilizable needles and syringes when you can no longer read the scale on the syringe, or if the needle is barbed.
- To test for barbs, carefully draw the needle across some cotton wool or gauze. If the needle is barbed it will catch in the cotton wool or gauze. In that case, dispose of the needle immediately.

1.1.4 Disposable syringes and needles

Disposable single-use syringes and needles are not recommended for injections in immunization programmes. Because reuse of disposable syringes and needles carries a high risk of infections, in 1999 WHO, UNICEF, and UNFPA issued a joint policy statement recommending against their use for immunization.

Vaccines that must be reconstituted, such as measles vaccine, require a large syringe to mix the diluent with the vaccine. While auto-disable reconstitution injection devices are the equipment of choice in these situations, they may not always be available. If this is the case, you may use disposable syringes and needles to reconstitute vaccine. Do not reuse the disposable syringe and needle for reconstitution.

Preventing needle-stick injuries and infections

Needles can be dangerous. Needles frequently injure health workers. Small but dangerous amounts of blood infected with hepatitis B, hepatitis C, HIV, or other viruses can be transmitted by needle-stick injuries. Needle-sticks may occur as follows:

- When health workers recap needles or walk while carrying used syringes and needles;
- If patients – especially children – are not positioned securely while they receive injections;
- If unsafe disposal practices leave

people or animals exposed to used syringes and needles.

How to prevent needle-stick injuries

This can be done by;

- ✓ Minimizing the need to handle needles and syringes;
- ✓ Handling syringes and needles safely;
- ✓ Setting up the immunization work area to reduce the risk of injury;
- ✓ Positioning children correctly for injections; and
- ✓ Practising safe disposal of all medical sharps waste.

MINIMIZING THE NEED TO HANDLE NEEDLES AND SYRINGES

Needle-stick injuries can occur at any time, but they happen most frequently during and immediately after an injection is given. In general, the more injection equipment is handled, the greater the risk of needle sticks. But needle sticks are preventable. There are simple steps health workers can follow to reduce the risk of needle-stick injuries. Minimizing the need to handle injection equipment is crucial to preventing injuries.

Here are some tips to minimize handling.

- ✓ Place a safety box close to the person giving vaccinations so used syringes and needles can be disposed of immediately.

- ✓ Avoid recapping the needle. If recapping is necessary (for example if the injection is delayed because the child is agitated), use a single-handed scoop technique.
- ✓ Do not manually remove the used needle from the syringe.
- ✓ Do not carry used syringes and needles around the immunization area or work site.
- ✓ When ready to vaccinate draw up the vaccine, inject the vaccine, and put the syringe in the safety box without putting it down between steps.
- ✓ Close the safety box securely when it is three-quarters full.
- ✓ Do not manually sort needles and syringes.

HANDLING SYRINGES AND NEEDLES SAFELY

You have to hold a syringe to give an injection. Any part of the syringe that you touch becomes contaminated, so you should not touch parts that come into contact with the vaccine or the child.

Do not touch: the shaft of the needle; the bevel of the needle; the adaptor of the needle; the adaptor of the syringe; and the plunger seal of the syringe. You may touch: the barrel; and the plunger top.

IMPORTANT: If any of these parts is touched, discard the syringe and needle and get new sterile ones.

PRACTICING SAFE DISPOSAL OF ALL MEDICAL SHARPS WASTE

Used injectables must be placed in a safety box and then disposed of in a safe manner. Follow the procedures for safe disposal outlined in the next section of this module to safely dispose of all injectable waste.

Disposing of used syringes and needles

Injection equipment should be discarded immediately after use once. The exception to this rule is sterilizable injection equipment which should be disposed of after about 50 uses.

Using a safety box

All used injection equipment except reusable syringes and needles should be placed in a safety box (*see Figure 2*) immediately after use. These containers are waterproof and tamper-proof and needles cannot easily pierce them. If a safety box is not available, you can use locally available materials to create a functional and safe used injectable container.

Figure 2: Safety box

How to assemble the safety box

Safety boxes require proper assembly before use. Many come with picture instructions printed on the side. *What to do if safety boxes are not available.*

Health workers can use strong cardboard boxes, thick plastic containers, or metal cans to collect syringes and needles and transport them to a site where they can be buried or burned. Do not reuse the same can or container after filling it once. Instead, destroy the container when it is three-quarters full and find a new container for your next session. Emptying and reusing safety boxes increases the risk of accidental needle-stick injuries and infection. Since it is recommended that all injectable waste be buried or burned, it is a good idea to use a disposal container made of cardboard if safety boxes are not available.

How to create a good sharps container:

- ✓ Find a strong cardboard box (your local shop may be able to help). If possible, the walls of the box should be strong enough that needles will not easily pierce the cardboard and prick someone handling the box.
- ✓ If necessary, strengthen the walls of the container by placing one box inside another. If the box is too thin, needles may stick through the sides of the box.
- ✓ Close the box securely, top and bottom.
- ✓ Cut a small hole in the top just big enough for a syringe and needle to enter.
- ✓ When the box is three-quarters full, seal the opening.
- ✓ Destroy the box carefully and completely.

To ensure safe handling of the safety box:

- ✓ Don't handle or shake the safety box more than necessary. Never squeeze, sit or stand on safety boxes.
- ✓ Take extra care when you are carrying the box to the disposal site. Hold the box by the top (by the handle provided) above the level of the needles and syringes.
- ✓ Keep safety boxes in a dry, safe place out of the reach of children and the general public, until they have been safely disposed of.
- ✓ Train everyone who will handle the box how to do it safely. Do not ask untrained staff to handle the box.

Procedures for disposing of injectable waste and injection equipment

All injection equipment must eventually be destroyed. Auto-disable or disposable mixing syringes and needles are used once and then destroyed. Used syringes and needles must NEVER be dumped in open areas where people might step on them or children might find them. They should never be disposed of along with other kinds of waste. Place the safety box within reach of the health worker. After each injection, immediately place the syringe and needle in the safety box or sharps container. Do not recap the needle.

Following the immunization session or when the safety box is three-quarters full, close the container. Do not transfer used syringes and needles from safety boxes to other containers. A five litre safety box can hold about 100 syringes and needles. When its three-quarter full, it should be destroyed as close as possible to the immunization session site, and as soon after the session as is practical.

Find a safe place to bury or burn the box.

CAUTION: Never put the following material in a safety box. Discard them separately with other medical waste: empty vials; discarded vaccine vials; cotton pads; compressors; dressing material; IV bags or extension tubes; latex gloves; or any kind of plastic materials or waste products.

DISPOSING OF SAFETY BOXES

Five methods are commonly used to destroy filled safety boxes or to keep them away from people. Any selected method of health care waste disposal must comply with national and sub national environmental regulations and with specific Ministry of Health instructions for your health centre.

❖ Incineration:

Incineration can completely destroy syringes and needles. Fires burning at temperatures higher than 800°C kill microorganisms and reduce the volume of waste to a minimum. Properly functioning incinerators

ensure the most complete destruction of syringes and needles. They produce less air pollution than fires burning at lower temperatures. Some hospitals have on-site incineration. The compound in which incineration takes place must be secure. Staff members conducting the incineration should wear safety glasses and heavy gloves.

❖ *Burning in a metal drum*

To burn in a metal drum or container;

- Choose a burning site in an unused area as far from buildings as possible. The area should be fenced and cleared.
- Place four bricks on the ground in a square pattern. Put a metal screen or grate on top of the bricks. Remove both ends of a 210-litre (55-US gallon) steel drum. This will allow air to flow through the drum and contents will burn better. If a metal drum is not available, you can build a cylinder from sheet metal, bricks, or clay.
- A chimney may be added to the removable top of the drum or container. Place the drum on top of a metal screen or grate.
- Put the filled safety boxes into the metal drum. Mix paper, leaves, or other flammable material in among the safety boxes to help them burn.
- Sprinkle a small amount of kerosene, if available, on the boxes and other material in the

drum. Place a fine metal screen over the top of the drum to reduce flying ashes.

- Put wood, paper, or other flammable material under the drum and ignite the material. Warn people to stay away and to avoid smoke, fumes, and ash from the fire.
- Allow the fire to burn until all of the safety boxes have been destroyed. Once the fire is out and the residue at the bottom of the drum has cooled, carefully collect the residue. Bury it in an unused location.
- Cover with at least 13 cm of soil. If possible, seal the residue pit with cement once it is full.

❖ *Open burning in a pit*

Open burning in a pit is not always recommended because burning plastic is not good for the environment. If you burn waste in the open.

- Choose an unused area for the burning site, as far from buildings as possible. The area should be fenced and cleared.
- Choose a qualified staff person to supervise the burn.
- Dig a pit at least one metre deep, but make sure it is not so deep that you will have to crawl into it to start the fire.

- Place the filled safety boxes in the pit. Mix paper, leaves, or other flammable materials among the boxes to help them burn.
- If available, sprinkle a small amount of kerosene and ignite the materials.
- Warn people to stay away and avoid smoke, fumes, and ash from the fire.
- Burns until all boxes are destroyed, and then follow the instructions above to bury residue.

❖ *Encapsulation:*

A specially made **safety pit** is another option to dispose of used syringes and needles that are loose. A safety pit is usually two metres deep and one metre in diameter so that it can be lined with a locally made concrete pipe. The pit has a concrete lid with a capped metal pipe set in it. Used syringes and needles are dropped through the metal pipe and into the pit.

❖ *Buried in a disposal pit:*

Used injection equipment may be buried in a disposal pit. Choose the site carefully and dig a pit large and

deep enough for bulky boxes (see Figure 4L). If contaminated AD syringes somehow escape from the box and are carried into streams or fields, people may step on them or children may play with them.

- Choose a site where people will not dig or establish latrines in the future.
- Fence off and clear the area.
- Dig a pit at least two metres deep. Make sure that the material will not escape from the pit, for example, during the rainy season.
- Take the filled safety boxes to the pit site just before burying. Do not open or empty the boxes.
- Place the filled safety boxes in the pit.
- Cover the boxes with at least 30 cm of soil. If possible, cover the site with concrete when the pit is full.

Make sure a qualified staff member supervises the process. Do not leave this vital task to unqualified people.

Conclusion

Proper handling and disposal of injection equipment is essential not just for the safety of humans, its effect on the environment should also be put

in proper perspective. This will ensure that even the farming activities around dumpsite benefit from safe waste management.

The following suggestions are therefore recommended to enhance safe wastes management and improved environmental aesthetics safety;

- Bestcontrol practices for intradermal, subcutaneous and intramuscular injections is recommended and the use of a new, single use injection device for each injection is suggested.
- A reliable, efficient, sustainable and environmentally method of SAFE disposal of injection equipments should be put in place urgently in all health facilities.

hospitals with modern waste disposal systems and equipment and there should be employment of more health workers for day - to - day cleaning of the hospitals.

- Training of more hospital health workers through attending conferences, seminars and workshops in order to increase their knowledge about hospital waste, its risks and sanitation is recommended and
- Government should enforce environmental sanitation by employing more health workers, and support them with materials and equipment for day-today operation.

• Government should support the
Figure 3: Open burning pit

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